

Scientific Productivity of Influential Pediatricians from Ten Arab Countries: Researchgate Analysis

Abstract

Background

Researchgate is an increasingly popular academic web site that has been increasingly used in the ranking of individual academics (physicians, scientists, researchers), and academic institutions. Scoring and ranking of individual academics in Researchgate is based mostly on the final RG Score for each academic.

Materials and Methods

More than 200 Researchgate profiles were examined during the first four days of December 2019 with aim of identifying influential pediatricians from ten Arab countries (Iraq, Jordan, Syria, Lebanon, UAE, Oman, Qatar, Bahrain, Yemen, Palestine) who have RG Score at Researchgate of 30 or higher.

Results

Only two pediatricians with RG Score at Researchgate of 30 or higher were identified from the 10 Arab countries. Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi has the highest RG Score of 32.44 and Rima Hanna-Wakim has RG Score of 30.95. Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi is affiliated to department of pediatrics and pediatric psychiatry consultation clinic, Children Teaching Hospital of Baghdad Medical City in Iraq, while Rima Hanna-Wakim is affiliated to department of pediatrics of the American University of Beirut. The main research fields of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi include neurology, psychiatry, nephrology, clinical genetics, while the main research fields of Rima Hanna-Wakim include infectious diseases, HIV, neonatal sepsis, immunology of infectious diseases, and respiratory viruses. Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi has 251 research items, 15,711 reads, and 291, whereas Rima Hanna-Wakim has 51 research items, (40 journal articles, 4 chapters, 5 conference papers, 1 data, and 1 project), 5,638 reads, and 738 citations.

Conclusion

During the first four days of December, 2019, Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi was the pediatrician with the highest RG score at Researchgate among pediatricians from Arab 10 countries.

Keywords: Research activities; Pediatricians; 10 Arab countries; Researchgate analysis.

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Research Article

Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi*

Children Teaching Hospital, Baghdad Medical City, Baghdad, Iraq

*Address for Correspondence

Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi, Senior Advisor, Doctor, Children Teaching Hospital, Baghdad Medical City, Baghdad, Iraq

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Introduction

Researchgate is an increasingly popular academic web site that has been increasingly used in the ranking of individual academics (physicians, scientists, researchers), and academic institutions. Scoring and ranking of individual academics in Researchgate is based mostly on the final RG Score for each academic which is measured using [1-6]:

- The quantitative academic output through the number of total publications.
- Total impact of the researcher through the cumulative impact factors o publications mostly journal articles.
- Measuring other impact indicators particularly the total number of the recorded downloads of full-text articles, and the total views of the meta-data of articles.

Materials and Methods

More than 200 Researchgate profiles were examined during the first four days of December 2019 with aim of identifying influential pediatricians from ten Arab countries (Iraq, Jordan, Syria, Lebanon, UAE, Oman, Qatar, Bahrain, Yemen, Palestine) who have RG Score at Researchgate of 30 or higher.

Results

Only two pediatricians with RG Score at Researchgate of 30 or higher were identified from the 10 Arab countries. Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi has the highest RG Score of 32.44 [7], and Rima Hanna-Wakim has RG Score of 30.95 [8]. Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi is affiliated to department of pediatrics and pediatric psychiatry consultation clinic, Children Teaching Hospital of Baghdad Medical City in Iraq, while Rima Hanna-Wakim is affiliated to department of pediatrics of the American University of Beirut. The main research fields of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi include neurology, psychiatry, nephrology, clinical genetics, while the main research fields of Rima Hanna-Wakim

include infectious diseases, HIV, neonatal sepsis, immunology of infectious diseases, and respiratory viruses. Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi has 251 research items, 15,711 reads, and 291, whereas Rima Hanna-Wakim has 51 research items, (40 journal articles, 4 chapters, 5 conference papers, 1 data, and 1 project), 5,638 reads, and 738 citations.

Discussion

Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi has been pioneering several fields of pediatrics in Iraq including pediatric nephrology, pediatric neuropsychiatry, and clinical genetics [9-11]. A Bibliometric study concluded that Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi is perfectly regarded as the undisputable pioneer of pediatric nephrology in Iraq. The paper emphasized that in 2008, the web site “Medical talks” listed Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi with the famous physicians in history for describing a new model for the treatment of chronic renal failure [10-12]. The study analyzed papers published by Iraqi pediatricians’ in the field of pediatric nephrology that were retrieved during the 22nd ad 23rd of August, 2019 from “Web of Science” and “PubMed”. Papers published by researchers other than pediatricians such urologic surgeons, and basic sciences researchers were not included in this study. The study found a total of 53 papers published in a total of 11 journals including Pediatric Nephrology, Therapy (Clinical practice), Journal of Tropical Pediatrics, Journal of Nephrology and Renal Transplantation, Urology, Clin Exp Nephrol, American Journal of Medical Genetics A, The Open Urology & Nephrology Journal, and Acta Paediatrica, Archives of Disease in Childhood, and Saudi Journal of Kidney Disease and Transplantation. The vast majority of papers, 49 (92.4%) were published by Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi. Only four other papers [Etiological and clinical patterns of childhood urolithiasis in Iraq (2005), .Profile of renal diseases in Iraqi children: A single-center report.(2015), Hypertension in hemodialyzed children (2016), The predictive factors for relapses in children with steroid-sensitive nephrotic syndrome (2016)] were published by authors other than Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi, and were carefully examined and found to include unreliable, non-authentic and largely misleading information. The study emphasized that the work of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi represented the authentic reliable source about childhood renal disorders in Iraq .The work of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi provided a comprehensive knowledge about childhood renal disorders in Iraqi children. The papers of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi in the field of nephrology included 12 research papers, 2 case report, one case series, three review articles, and at least 31 conferences’ abstracts [11, 12].

The papers of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi included descriptions of the patterns of various childhood disorders including acute glomerulonephritis, chronic renal failure, renal tubular disorders including nephropathic cystinosis, oculo-cerebro-renal syndrome , Hinman syndrome. He described the challenges in the treatment of chronic renal failure in Iraq and in the developing world. Aamir Al-Mosawi described a new model for the management of chronic renal failure, and reported six-year dialysis freedom in a girl with end-stage renal disease. This new model has become increasingly known as

dietary on intestinal dialysis. Aamir Al-Mosawi also described a new conservative management for childhood urolithiasis and also a new therapeutic approach for the treatment of refractory vitamin D-resistant rickets. He also described ocular abnormalities in childhood chronic renal failure, and reported the association of renal agenesis with Coffin Siris syndrome. Aamir Al-Mosawi also described the new association of idiopathic hyperuricosuria, hypercalciuria and infantile renal stone disease and suggested a therapeutic approach for its treatment [11-16]. There is no doubt that Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi has also been pioneering the fields of clinical genetics and dysmorphology as he has more than 30 publications contributing to these fields. This fact applies also to the fields of pediatric neurology and psychiatry with more than 25 publications contributing to these fields .His contribution to non-genetic rare disorders can not be ignored . His pioneering publications in Iraq made Aamir Al-Mosawi, the Iraqi pediatrician and hospital-based clinician with the highest H-index in Scopus [7,9,17,18].

Conclusion

During the first four days of December 2019, Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi was the pediatrician with the highest RG score at Researchgate among pediatricians from Arab 10 countries.

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References

1. www.researchgate.net.
2. Madisch IM (2008) ResearchGate scientific network: A first step towards science 2.0. *Clinical and Experimental Immunology* 154: 214.
3. Mark C (2011) Biologists Using Social-networking Sites to Boost Collaboration". *BioScience* 61: 736.
4. Chakraborty N (2012) Activities and reasons for using social networking sites by research scholars in NEHU: A study on Facebook and ResearchGate. *Planner*: 19-27.
5. Thelwall M, Kousha K (2014) ResearchGate: Disseminating, communicating, and measuring Scholarship? *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology* 66: 876-889.
6. Chun YM, Jim WY, Alhalabi W, Yun KH (2016) ResearchGate: An effective altmetric indicator for active researchers?" *Computers in Human Behavior* 55: 1001-1006.
7. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Aamir_Al_Mosawi [Accessed: 1-4, December, 2014].
8. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Rima_Hanna-Wakim [Accessed: 1-4, December, 2014].
9. Al-Mosawi AJ (2019) The scientific productivity and academic output of elite Iraqi pediatricians: h-index reliability indicators. *International Journal of Research*

Studies in Medical and Health Sciences 4: 3-6.

10. Al-Mosawi AJ (2019) Scientific publication productivity and research activities of Iraqi pediatricians in the field of pediatric nephrology: A bibliometric Analysis to identify pioneers. *Advancements in Journal of Urology and Nephrology* 1: 1-10.
11. Al-Mosawi AJ (2019) Scientific productivity of Iraqi pediatricians in pediatric nephrology. 1st ed., Saarbrücken; LAP Lambert Academic Publishing.
12. Only medical talks [Accessed on the 3rd of December, 2019].
13. Al-Mosawi AJ (2011) Intestinal dialysis: A new therapy for chronic renal failure. 1st ed., Saarbrücken; LAP Lambert Academic Publishing.
14. Al-Mosawi AJ (2013) A new dietary therapy for chronic renal failure. 1st ed., Saarbrücken; LAP Lambert Academic Publishing.
15. Al-Mosawi AJ (2017) Advances of peritoneal dialysis in the developing world: Combined intermittent peritoneal dialysis and intestinal dialysis, In Ed, *Peritoneal Dialysis: Practices, Complications and Outcomes*.
16. Al-Mosawi AJ (2019) Dietary dialysis with acacia gum: Intestinal dialysis Technology. *Advancements in Journal of Urology and Nephrology* 2: 1-8.
17. Al-Mosawi AJ (2019) Researchgate activity of elite pediatricians from ten Arab countries: Researchgate analysis. 1st ed., Baghdad; Iraq Headquarter of Copernicus Scientists International Panel Publishing.
18. Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi. [Accessed on the 3rd of December, 2019].

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